

SELF- EFFICACY AND GOAL PERSPECTIVE: INPUTS TO WORK MOTIVATION, IMPROVEMENT AND ACCOMPLISHMENT OF TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to investigate the relationship between self – efficacy and goal perspective inputs to work motivation, improvement and accomplishment of teachers in Fule- Almeda District, Division of San Pablo. Teaching in the 21st century poses many challenges for teachers, and thus, they need to take on more roles in their schools to meet the expectations of students, parents and the school community. Based on the perceived level of teacher’s self-efficacy the responses are significantly related to work motivation, improvement and accomplishment. With students’ engagement has the highest mean. Believing in innate abilities means valuing one’s set of cognitive strengths. It is the perceptions of successful or less successful teaching experiences, including experiences of classroom management, instructing and motivating students, and cooperating with colleagues and parents. Likewise based on the responses it found out that teachers’ goal perspective is significantly related to work motivation, improvement and accomplishment. Preparedness was found out to have a highest mean score states that readiness is a great factor before facing the students. Specifically, a task-oriented individual is assumed to choose a challenging task, exert maximum effort, experience intrinsic interest, and persist in the task, even in the face of difficulty to achieve a meaningful goal. The parameters on self-efficacy and goal perspective have a direct contribution to the work improvement and accomplishment of teachers. Work improvement has become an important practice in the daily lives of educators. Modern forms of professional development that allow educators to customize learning environments have the potential to not only shape and propel practice forward, but also to empower teachers, improve their work and redefine their identities as professionals. The result of the study will be beneficial to both the teachers and the management. The most helpful thing a teacher can do is empower students to succeed by providing them with a learning environment that respects, embraces, and celebrates their diversity.

Keywords: self – efficacy, goal perspective, task-oriented, empower